

As can be observed, the hardness of both the composite and the corresponding unreinforced matrix for each copper alloy selected is quite similar, except for the CuCrZr based composite which exhibits approximately a ten percent increase. Moreover, the higher the alumina fiber V_f incorporated inside the matrix, the harder the material, as can be checked for the CuAlNiFe based composite. In this case, the higher alumina fiber content composite is harder than the corresponding unreinforced matrix, when, on contrary, the low alumina fiber content composite is softer than the respective matrix. In general, the hardness of the MMCs reinforced with ceramic particles or fibers is higher than that shown by the unreinforced matrix. However, although in the present work it has not been always the case, it might be attributed to the presence of the soft graphite flakes (hardness of 0.25 GPa) which could be responsible for the relatively low hardness values obtained for the composites in comparison with those initially expected.

Coefficient of Thermal Expansion (CTE)

The high CTE value traditionally shown by copper and its alloys is one of the main physical properties which is required to be notably improved for their application in several potential components such as electronics [6]. In this way, a great improvement of the CTE value can be obtained by means of CuMCs due to the very low thermal expansion reinforcements available in the market for its incorporation inside metallic matrices. For example, the high stiffness long carbon fibers which have a CTE value close to zero in the fiber axis direction and allow the obtention of CuMCs with a very low CTE for a high V_f of carbon fibers, as has been reported in other previous studies [7].

Table 4 shows the CTE values measured for two CuMCs reinforced with a mixture of graphite flakes ($V_f = 7\%$) and δ -alumina short fibers ($V_f = 6\%$) each one, and the corresponding values measured for their unreinforced matrices. A slight reduction of the CTE value, in the range of temperatures studied, has been obtained for both composites in respect to the unreinforced corresponding matrices, due to the reinforcements incorporated which have a considerably lower CTE value.

Table 4: Measured Coefficients of Thermal Expansion

Material	Coefficient of Thermal Expansion α ($\times 10^{-6}$ m/m $^{\circ}$ C)			
	100 $^{\circ}$ C	200 $^{\circ}$ C	300 $^{\circ}$ C	400 $^{\circ}$ C
CuSn alloy	15.65	16	16.36	16.88
CuSn based composite	15.24	15.40	15.65	16.07
CuAlNiFe alloy	15.21	15.45	16.01	17.02
CuAlNiFe based composite	14.22	14.55	15.43	16.32

On the other hand, the variation of the CTE versus the test temperature in the range of temperatures studied is very small for both composites, as in the case of the respective unreinforced matrices. Although the four materials presented a linear behaviour until the 200 $^{\circ}$ C test temperature, the slope for their evolution of the CTE with the test temperature was

continuously increasing after that temperature until 400 °C, as can be checked through the data presented in this Table.

Friction Behaviour

The Fig.2 shows the measured coefficient of sliding friction as a function of the sliding time for both a CuSn bronze alloy and its based composite reinforced with a mixture of graphite flakes ($V_f=7\%$) and δ -alumina short fibers ($V_f=6\%$).

The evolution of the friction coefficient versus time, enables two different states to be distinguished. The transient state develops at the beginning of the friction test, during about the first ten or fifteen minutes, which is characterized by an increase of the friction coefficient (state 1) followed by a decrease until a permanent steady state is reached (state 2).

Fig.2: Coefficient of friction vs. test duration

In this steady state and considering a load of 500 g, the coefficient of friction for the composite is close to 0.17 and about one third lower of that of the unreinforced alloy. The highly pronounced wear track in the alloy suggested that the load applied was too great to allow a correct estimation of the coefficient of friction. Thus, a lower applied weight of 200 g was used later on. The coefficient of friction measured in the steady state condition is quite similar but the wear track was still significant.

Wear Behaviour

The wear behaviour was also studied with the same materials used for evaluating the coefficient of friction: a CuSn alloy and a composite based on this alloy and reinforced with a mixture of graphite flakes ($V_f=7\%$) and δ -alumina short fibers ($V_f=6\%$).

Firstly, the plot of the measured CuSn matrix weight loss as a function of the sliding velocity and applied load is presented in the following Fig.3. As is shown, keeping the applied load constant, the sample weight loss increases linearly when increasing the sliding speed from 67 mm/s to 133 mm/s. Moreover, the heavier the load applied on the sample at a constant speed, the higher the weight loss. Considering that the sliding speed is connected to the sliding

distance as a result of a similar wear track length in each test, the wear rate can be defined as the weight loss per unit of sliding distance [8]. Then, the higher the load applied on the sample, the greater the wear rate being otherwise constant for a given load. For example, at a weak load of 2.34 kg, the wear rate is constant around 3.5×10^{-4} g/m, when it is close to 2×10^{-3} g/m for a heavy load of 10.53 kg.

Fig.3: CuSn matrix weight loss vs. the sliding speed

As far as the composite tested is concerned, only one sample of the five studied gave rise to a significant weight loss. Thus, considering both an applied load of 7.02 kg and a sliding speed of 133 mm/s, the composite weight loss was ten times lower than that of the unreinforced matrix. In the same way, the composite weight loss was five hundred times lower under conditions of load and speed such as 2.34 kg and 100 mm/s. For any other combinations of load and applied weight of those shown in the Table 2, the four samples left did suffer very low wear, that is, a wear giving rise to a non-significant sample weight difference before and after the test. Furthermore, by applying more severe wear conditions such as a speed of 166 mm/s and a load of 30 kg, the composite sample did not exhibit measurable weight loss either.

Wear Mechanisms

The Fig.4 shows a micrograph of the wear track after the wear testing carried out for a CuSn copper alloy under a load and speed of 2.34Kg and 67 mm/s respectively.

The wear seems to be controlled by an adhesion mechanism. Adhesive wear occurs when two metallic components slide against each other under a given applied load, and no abrasive is presented [9]. This type of wear is called “adhesive” because of the strong metallic bonds created between surface asperities of both the sample and the counterpart material. Wear results from plastic deformation and shear failure of the weaker of the two metallic surfaces. In theory, when the applied load is low enough, the oxide film present at the surface of the sample can prevent the formation of metallic bonds between the asperities of the sliding surfaces, resulting in low wear rates. This form of wear is called “mild wear”. When the applied load is high, metallic bonds are formed between the surface asperities and the resulting wear rates are high. Thus, it is called “severe wear”. As shown in the Fig.4, the wear mechanism is severe wear. The oxide film at the surface of the bronze is continuously dispersed at the point of contact of each material as a result of the tangential motion at the

interface. Thus, the oxide film can not act as a lubricant which results in a mechanism of severe wear. During the wear test against steel, bronze particles are produced giving rise to a great amount of debris. Also, some of the debris is not ejected from the track but spread again on the surface. By optical examination, a few particles of bronze are seen to have transferred to steel where they remain attached, but most sliding surface of the steel ball remains undisturbed.

Fig.4: Micrograph of the CuSn bronze alloy wear track

The wear track resulting from the sliding wear of a CuSn based composite against steel under a load and speed of 2.34 Kg and 67 mm/s respectively, is shown in Fig.5 below.

Fig.5: Micrograph of the CuSn/Graphite - Alumina composite wear track

In most samples, whatever the wear conditions, there is nearly neither wear loss, nor grooves and the plastic deformation is low. However, a fine discontinuous graphite layer is dispersed at the surface of the track avoiding metal-to-metal contact. The graphite in the composite is flake graphite and due to its anisotropic crystal structure, it has lubricating properties. During the wear event, the shear stresses lead to a shear process of the graphite flakes. Afterwards, the graphite forms a film on the surface of the wear track and protects the bulk material from adhesion wear. By optical examination, a few grooves can be noticed at the surface of the steel balls with some graphite dispersed at a few points. The wear of the ball may result from a mechanism of abrasive wear induced by the presence of the δ -alumina short fibers inside the matrix. They are also supposed to increase the hardness of the composite giving rise to low plastic deformation around the wear track. Thus, mixing ceramic fibers with lubricant graphite in a metal is a good way of improving the copper tribological properties, reducing both the friction coefficient and the wear tendency of the metallic matrix.

CONCLUSIONS

1. The CuMCs tested have shown a hardness similar to that measured for the corresponding unreinforced matrices, except for the CuCrZr based composite which has presented a ten percent increase. However, the hardness of the composites has been higher in comparison with the matrix for that based on a CuAlNiFe alloy and reinforced with the highest V_f of δ -alumina short fibers used (7%).
2. The coefficient of thermal expansion shown by both CuSn and CuAl copper alloys has been slightly reduced through the incorporation of a 13% final V_f of a mixture of both graphite flakes and δ -alumina short fibers for the range of temperatures tested.
3. The coefficient of friction for the CuSn based composite is around 0.17, being three times lower than that shown by the unreinforced copper alloy.
4. The CuSn based composite shows excellent wear resistance compared to that shown by the unreinforced bronze alloy. For example, the composite weight loss is five hundred times lower under a load of 2.34 kg and a speed of 100 mm/s. Moreover, after a 30 min. wear test under a load and speed of 30 kg and 166 mm/s respectively, the composite did not exhibit higher wear loss than in the former specified conditions.
5. The CuSn bronze alloy weight loss increases linearly when the sliding velocity is increased. Moreover, the heavier the load applied at a constant speed, the higher the weight loss, and the higher the load applied, the greater the wear rate.
6. The tribological properties of the CuSn based composite are mainly attributed to the thin layer of graphite at the surface of the wear track, impeding metal-to-metal contact responsible for the adhesion wear process suffered by the CuSn alloy. The graphite in the composite is flake graphite and due to its anisotropic crystal structure, it has lubricant properties. The δ -alumina short fibers mixed inside the metal are also supposed to play a significant role, giving the composite a higher hardness than the matrix. Consequently, it is not surprising that both the plastic deformation around the wear track and the composite weight loss are low. Thus, mixing ceramic fibers with lubricant graphite in a metal is a good way of improving the composite tribological

properties, reducing both the friction coefficient and the wear tendency of the metallic matrix.

7. Further optimization of the composite processing parameters has to be carried out in order to obtain more homogeneous properties.

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